

Original Research Report

Awareness of Nutrition in Pregnancy among Newly Married Women in Uzo-Uwani Local Government Area, Enugu State, Nigeria

Blessing Ijeoma Attah^{1*}

¹Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, P.M.B. 41001 Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria

***Correspondence:** Blessing Ijeoma Attah, Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, P.M.B. 41001 Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria (Email: ijeoma.attah@unn.edu.ng)

Abstract: The study investigated the awareness of nutrition in pregnancy among newly married women. The research adopted a survey research design. Three specific objectives and three research questions were proposed for the study, while null hypotheses were developed and assessed at the 0.05 level of significance. A stratified random sampling was used to select 102 newly married women in Uzo- Uwani LGA, Enugu State, Nigeria. For data collection, a structured questionnaire with 30 questions was used. Three professionals verified the tool. To address the research questions, mean and standard deviation were employed, while the t-test was used to examine the null hypotheses. The findings of the study indicated that newly married women engaged in unhealthy feeding practices. The newly married women's awareness and interaction about nutrition in pregnancy were shown to be adequate. There were several sources of nutrition awareness among the women, including radio (91%), health workers (83.3%), friends (78.4%), family members (71%), television (64.5%) and posters (44.1%).

Keywords: Awareness, Feeding Practices, Married Women, Nutrition, Pregnancy

1. Introduction

Nutrition is the sciences that deals with all the various factors of which food is composed and the way it works, nutrition allows a control and creates awareness of the types of nutrients entering the digestive system, and significantly control certain changes in blood glucose levels. Nutrition in pregnancy refers to the nutritional intake and dietary planning that occurs before, during, and after pregnancy. The nutrition of the fetus begins from conception. As a result, maternal nutrition is critical both before conception (possibly many months before) and during pregnancy (Haider & Bhutta, 2015). Before conception is the ideal time to create a condition of optimum health and nutrition. In various areas, dietary and nutritional recommendations for pregnant women differ from those for adult women in general.

Eating a nutritious diet can assist pregnant women in promoting proper growth and development during their pregnancy, as well as ensuring that their infants are born healthy, on time, and with the mental, physical, and psychological ability to grow and develop normally. A nutritious diet also helps protect the mother's health (Bredbenner et al., 2009). Maternal physiological changes during pregnancy are so substantial that they were formerly thought to be abnormal and need to be remedied. Doctors routinely urged pregnant patients to adopt low-sodium diets to decrease water retention, to restrict their weight growth and calorie consumption to avoid difficulties after birth, and to take excessive amounts of iron and other supplements to restore their blood nutrient levels to "normal". We now know that pregnancy affects what was previously thought to be a normal physiological state in non-pregnant women.

Fortunately, it is now understood that attempts to reverse physiological changes in a non-pregnant mother may have a negative impact on the pregnancy. The mother must first increase the amount of plasma that can be circulated in order to provide the fetus with enough energy, nutrients, and oxygen for development. Then, maternal nutritional reserves are built up. These reserves are accumulated in advance to accommodate significant increases in fetal weight. Similar to how fetal weight increase determines the maximal rate of placental growth. This sequence of procedures ensures that the placenta has all it needs to perform at a high level while the fetal weight increases swiftly. Fetuses rely on the operation of various systems that have been established long in advance of their maximum rates of growth and development (Elliott-Sale et al., 2019).

Pregnancy is one of the most nutritionally demanding times in a woman's life. A mother's body delivers all the energy and nutrients required to grow a newborn 5000 times larger than the fertilized egg in around 9 months. A pregnant woman requires more calories and more of practically every nutrient than a non-pregnant woman. The extra calories and nutrients help the fetus grow and develop, as well as the mother's body and improved maternal metabolism. A pregnant woman should consume more nutrient-dense foods to satisfy her calorie and nutritional demands. Metabolic changes that allow pregnant women to utilize certain nutrients more efficiently (e.g., proteins), absorb others better (e.g., calcium, iron), and/or excrete less of others (e.g., zinc, riboflavin) also contribute to meeting pregnancy's calorie and nutritional needs. A sufficient amount of calories and all nutrients are required for a successful pregnancy (Eze et al., 2018).

The period between conception and delivery is known as pregnancy. An egg becomes a placenta, an embryo, and then a fetus after being fertilized by a sperm and placed in the uterine lining. A normal pregnancy lasts 40 weeks and is broken up into three trimesters of three months each. It usually starts on the first day of the woman's last menstrual cycle. Pregnancy, or gestation, may be the most vulnerable period of the life cycle, with food and calorie sources influencing the result. To help ensure the optimal health of both the mother and her offspring, adequate nutrient is vital both before and during pregnancy. Conception starts hundreds of sophisticated and sequential biological processes that transform two connected cells into the next generation of humans. Because of the rapid growth of structures and functions in both the mother and the fetus, as well as the time-sensitive nature of energy and food requirements, maternal nutritional health is an essential component of successful reproduction. Conception happens around 14 days before the start of a woman's next menstrual cycle. Pregnancy lasts an average of 38 weeks, or 266 days, as measured from conception.

Three different types of pregnancy exist: ectopic pregnancy, molar pregnancy, and intrauterine pregnancy. Ectopic pregnancy occurs when a fertilized egg implants outside of the uterus, molar pregnancy occurs when tissue that would normally become a fetus instead becomes an abnormal growth inside the uterus, and intrauterine pregnancy occurs when the fetus or fetuses implant inside the uterus. On the inside of the uterus, the placenta is connected to the uterine muscle. A kind of ectopic pregnancy known as intra-abdominal pregnancy occurs when the baby grows inside the abdominal cavity. When one egg and one sperm combine to form one child, this is known as a singlet pregnancy. When two sperm penetrate one egg or when one sperm fertilizes one egg and splits into two zygotes, multiple pregnancy results. If more than one egg is fertilized, the pregnancy will end in fraternal twins. Fraternal twins would result from the fertilization of one egg by two sperm. One egg can divide into multiple zygotes, leading to identical twins; lupus pregnancy; lupus is an auto-immune disease; high risk pregnancy; women over 35; those carrying multiples; and those with diabetes and other conditions that could affect pregnancy are all likely to experience pregnancy complications more frequently. A pregnancy may be labeled high-risk if the expectant mother needs to take medication to treat certain medical conditions that might damage the fetus.

A pregnant woman requires more calories to sustain the development of both her own tissues and the fetus's. Furthermore, more calories are required to support the increased metabolic demand that pregnancy places on a woman's heart, lungs, and other organs. A daily increase of roughly 350 calories is advised during the second trimester. Additionally, a daily increase of around 450 calories is advised throughout the third trimester. Women who are overweight or obese at the start of their pregnancy should aim for a somewhat lower increase in calories. Those in their twenties, underweight, or physically active may most likely require more calories in fact, compared to underweight women who do not increase their energy intake, overweight women who do so are more likely to have healthier kids and experience fewer infant fatalities. Women who are physically active throughout pregnancy may need to increase their calorie intake by more than 350 to 450 calories since their increased body weight need more energy for action (Elliott-Sale et al., 2019).

Pregnant women are advised to consume more protein than women who are not pregnant. For optimal prenatal growth and development, especially of the brain and vision, essential fatty acids are necessary. Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), an omega-3 fatty acid, should be consumed in sufficient amounts to optimize pregnancy outcomes, including birth weight, length, and head circumference. Many women need to raise the proportion of Omega-3 fats in their diets relative to Omega-6 fats. Folate and vitamin B-12 are required for DNA synthesis as well as the formation of fetal and maternal cells. When folate levels are low, fewer red blood cells are produced, resulting in folate anemia. Inadequate folate consumption can result in premature birth, low birth weight, fetal growth retardation, spontaneous abortion, poor placenta development, and other pregnancy complications (Roberts et al., 2010). Choose a variety of nutritious foods from the following group to develop your healthy pregnancy diet: fruits: 3–4 servings daily. Opt for fresh fruit. 3-5 servings of vegetables, 3 servings of dairy products, and 2–3 servings of proteins should be consumed daily. Choose lean cuts of meat, poultry, fish, and eggs that have been cooked with little or no fat. Three servings of whole grains each day. A maximum of six servings of grains should be consumed each day, at least half of which should be whole grains. Fiber is a key component of whole grain foods like bread, cereal, and pasta during pregnancy.

Nutrition in pregnancy awareness is consumption of adequate meals during pregnancy to help mother and child. Aid to help proper development of embryo and fetus simultaneously (Mahmood et al., 2013). As a result, nutritional awareness is a precondition for nutritional literacy (the contextualized and detailed understanding of issues and problems, which allow one to evaluate and make nutrition decisions). In the view of Uche (2013), the importance of helping people develop their nutritional awareness, through an awareness of the relationship between nutrition and human life requires a special significance. Nutrition awareness encompasses incorporating knowledge of contemporary nutrition issues affecting humans locally and beyond, discovering which actions (nutrition practices) can make a difference in one's health status, and self-awareness concerning food consumption (Venkiteshwaran et al., 2015).

1.1. Statement of Problem

Inadequate awareness and knowledge of available foods and their nutritional values can be contributed to inappropriate feeding practices, which on the long run, causes nutrition-related diseases. According to the United States Department of Agriculture and US Department of Health & Human Services (2012), people's awareness of or implicit presumptions about food are important factors in determining their dietary choices. Therefore, one crucial aspect that may affect dietary choices and nutritional intake is one's own opinion of the classification of foods and their nutritious worth. When trying to state their cravings, newlywed pregnant women confront difficulties with flavor, quality, affordability, and health—but more crucially, with nutrition awareness and food knowledge.

Because of the nature of their habitat and employment (farming), newly married women are forced to consume whatever is available in their area. Nutrition awareness, on the other hand, is influenced by knowledge received via one's own views or from information shared. Because nutritional awareness is synonymous with nutritional literacy, perfect nutritional awareness would

enable newly married women to make educated dietary choices and engage in appropriate nutritional practices. As a result, this study was necessary to determine the nutritional knowledge level of newly married women in Uzo-Uwani.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The study's main goal was to look into newly married women's knowledge of nutrition during pregnancy in Uzo-Uwani Local Government Area, Enugu State.

The study specifically determined:

- (a) Awareness and interaction levels about nutrition among newly married women in Uzo-uwani L.G.A.
- (b) Feeding practices commonly adopted by newly married women in Uzo- Uwani L.G.A.
- (c) Sources of awareness of nutrition among newly married women in Uzo- Uwani L.G.A.

1.3. Research Questions

- (a) What are the awareness and interaction levels about nutrition among newly married women in Uzo- Uwani?
- (b) What are the newly married women awareness levels on feeding practices commonly adopted by newly married women in Uzo- Uwani L.G.A?
- (c) What are the awareness levels of newly married women on the sources of awareness of nutrition?

1.4 Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses will serve as the study's framework and were tested at the 0.05 significance level.

H₀₁: The mean rating of the awareness and interaction levels about nutrition among newly married women in Uzo- Uwani does not significantly differ from one another.

H₀₂: The mean rating of the newly married women living at Adani community of Uzo-Uwani and those living at Nrobo community on feeding practices does not significantly differ from one another.

H₀₁: The mean rating of newly married women living at Nkpologu community and those living at Ugbuneajima community on the sources of awareness of nutrition does not significantly differ from one another.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The study used a descriptive survey approach as research design and it was considered suitable because it helps to study people's attitudes, motivation and other characteristics.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The study was carried out with informed oral consent, anonymity, and confidentiality of the respondents. The data was collected with strict compliance regarding ethical demands of respondents; data protection management as required in research studies.

2.2. Area of the Study

The research was conducted out in Uzo-Uwani town, which is located in Enugu state, Nigeria.

2.3. Population and Sample

The target population for the study consisted of those who are married within one month to twelve months in Uzo- Uwani town from 15 years and above (Umuada) totaling 1,454. There are 10 towns in Uzo-Uwani. (Age grade of different towns, 2022).

2.3.1. Sample for the Study

The sample for the study comprised of approximately 8% of 1545 newly married women. Multistage sampling technique was used to select four towns from the 10 towns that make up Uzo-Uwani LGA

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

To obtain data, a questionnaire was employed. The sections dealt with the specific objectives of the study. Three specialists from the Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education validated the instrument. Reliability index after pilot testing stood at 0.795.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The total number 102 copies of questionnaire were administered to respondents by the researcher. Interpretation was made to those that were not educated. The completed questionnaires were collected immediately from the respondents by the researcher. The questionnaire was administered within an interval of two weeks.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

The data collected were analyzed using means, standard deviation and t-test. Mean rating of 2.00 and above were considered extremely true while below 2.00 were considered not true.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. *Research question one:* What are the awareness and interaction levels about nutrition among newly married women in Uzo- Uwani?

Table 1: Mean responses on the newly married women's awareness and interaction levels about nutrition

No	Awareness and Interaction	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1.	The body gets its energy from carbohydrates.	3.79	0.15	EA
2.	Extra energy is stored as fat in the body.	3.48	0.06	MA
3.	Protein is necessary for the synthesis and maintenance of bodily tissues.	3.62	0.35	EA
4.	Oil and fats are sources of energy.	3.78	0.24	EA
5.	Vitamin and mineral-rich diets are protective foods.	3.68	0.88	EA
6.	Vitamin C aids in scurvy prevention.	3.75	0.72	EA
7.	Water helps the body remove waste items from it.	3.32	1.66	MA
8.	Strong bones and teeth are maintained and built with the aid of calcium.	3.84	0.52	EA
9.	Bone health benefits of milk and other dairy products are significant.	3.61	0.51	EA
10.	Water supplies nutrition to the body's cells.	3.36	1.06	MA

Keys: \bar{X} Mean, SD Standard Deviation, EA Extremely Aware, MA Moderately Aware

Table 1 revealed the awareness and interaction levels about nutrition among the newly married

women. The awareness and interaction with extreme levels include: the body gets its energy from carbohydrates (3.79), protein is necessary for the synthesis and maintenance of bodily tissues (3.62), oil and fats are sources of energy (3.38), vitamin and mineral-rich diets are protective foods (3.68), vitamin c aids in scurvy prevention (3.75), strong bones and teeth are maintained and built with the aid of calcium (3.84), bone health benefits of milk and other dairy products are significant (3.61). The awareness and interaction with moderate levels includes: extra energy is stored as fat in the body (3.48), water assists in removing waste products from the body (3.32), and water supplies nutrition to the body's cells (3.36). This shows that newly married women awareness and interaction levels about nutrition were adequate.

3.2. *Research question two:* What are the newly married women’s awareness levels on feeding practices?

Table 2: Mean responses on awareness level of newly married women in Uzo- Uwani

No	Feeding practices commonly adopted by newly married women	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1.	Consumption of fast foods	3.58	0.52	MA
2.	omitting breakfast and having lunch and supper	3.44	0.71	EA
3.	Take breakfast to farm/work	2.29	1.15	EA
4.	Eat in – between meals	3.50	0.30	EA
5.	Skipping Lunch	3.10	0.71	MA
6.	Consume snacks as meals or lunch	3.86	1.37	EA
7.	Eat adequate meals three times daily	2.67	0.53	MA
8.	Take soft drink daily	3.67	0.39	EA
9.	Take dinner at 8pm daily	2.00	0.00	MA
10.	Eating from food vendors	1.56	0.32	MA

Keys: EA Extremely Aware, MA Moderately Aware

Table 2 revealed the awareness level of newly married women awareness level on feeding practices. The feeding practice with highest awareness level and most commonly adopted is that newly married consume snacks as meals or lunch (3.86), take soft drink daily (3.67), consumption of food from fast foods(3.58), eat in between meals (3.50), omitting breakfast and having lunch and supper (3.44), skipping lunch (3.10), eat adequate meals three times daily (2.67), take breakfast to farm /work (2.29), take dinner at 8pm daily (2.00) and the feeding practice with least mean is eating from food vendors (1.56). The table also demonstrated that the standard deviations SD of the items are within the range.

3.3. *Research question three:* What are the awareness levels of newly married women on the sources of awareness of nutrition among newly married women in Uzo- Uwani L.G.A?

Table 3: Percentage responses on awareness levels of newly married women in Uzo- Uwani

No	Sources of Nutrition Information	Number	Percentage %
1.	Television	66	64.5%
2.	Radio	93	91.1%
3.	Internet	28	27.5%
4.	Health workers	85	83.3%

5.	Newspapers	39	38.2%
6.	Posters	45	44.1%
7.	Food labels	30	29.4%
8.	Billboard	20	20%
9.	Friends	80	78.4%
10.	Family members	72	71%

Keys: N = Number of Respondents, %= Percentage

The data in Table 3 indicated that there are various sources of nutrition information awareness for newly married women. The radio (91%) has the highest percentage followed by health workers (83.3%), friends (78.4%), family members (71%), television (64.5%) and posters (44.1%). The nutrition source with least percentage is billboard (20%), internet (27.5%), food labels (29.4%) and newspaper (38.2%).

3.4. Test of Hypotheses

The t-test was used to examine the two hypotheses. Tables 4 and 5 provide an overview of the analysis for the two null hypotheses.

3.4.1. Null Hypothesis One (H_{01}): The mean rating of the awareness and interaction about nutrition among newly married women in Uzo- Uwani does not significantly differ from one another.

Table 4 (Cluster 1): Independent samples t-test on levels of awareness and interaction about nutrition among newly married women in Uzo – Uwani

S/NO	Item Statements	\bar{X}_G	Town	N	\bar{X}	SD	F-Cal	P	Decision
1	Carbohydrates provides energy for the body	3.58	ADANI	54	3.54	0.54	1.74	0.33	NS
			NROBO	47	3.64	0.49			
2	Extra energy is stored as fat in the body.	3.44	ADANI	54	3.50	0.67	0.77	0.33	NS
			NROBO	47	3.36	0.76			
3	Protein is needed for building and repair of body tissues	2.29	ADANI	54	2.20	1.35	3.35	0.51	NS
			NROBO	47	2.38	1.36			
4	Fats and oils are energy source	3.90	ADANI	54	3.89	0.32	0.76	0.67	NS
			NROBO	47	3.91	0.28			
5	Foods from vitamins and Minerals sources are protective foods	4.00	ADANI	54	4.00	0.00	1.33	0.42	NS
			NROBO	47	4.00	0.00			
6	Vitamin C helps prevent scurvy	3.86	ADANI	54	3.83	0.42	0.32	0.32	NS
			NROBO	47	3.89	0.31			
7	Water assists in removing waste products from the body.	3.67	ADANI	54	3.72	0.45	0.05	0.80	NS
			NROBO	47	3.62	0.61			
8	Calcium helps to maintain and build strong bone and teeth	3.67	ADANI	54	3.69	0.51	1.02	0.59	NS
			NROBO	47	3.66	0.48			

9	Milk and other dairy products are important for bone	4.00	ADANI	54	4.00	0.00	2.08	0.48	NS
			NROBO	47	4.00	0.00			
10	Water transports nutrients to cells in the body	1.56	ADANI	54	1.69	1.17	0.22	0.24	NS
			NROBO	47	1.42	1.14			
Mean Cluster		3.40	ADANI	54	3.60	0.36	0.33	0.89	NS
			NROBO	47	3.20	0.37			

Keys: \bar{X}_G Grand Mean, \bar{X} Mean of individual groups, N Group sizes, SD Standard Deviation, F-Cal F-Calculated, p-Value, NS Not Significant, S Significant, df = 99

The results in Table 4 for cluster 1 indicated that the p-value for each item is larger than 0.05 (p-value > 0.05). The cluster mean in Table 4, however, indicated that the p-value was more than 0.05 (p-value > 0.05), and as a result, the cluster mean was not statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance. This suggests that there is no appreciable difference in the mean ratings of newlywed members of the Adani and Nrobo communities on awareness and interaction levels about nutrition. The null hypothesis was therefore supported.

3.4.2. Null Hypothesis Two (H_{02}): The mean rating of the newly married women living at Adani community of Uzo-Uwani and those living at Nrobo community on feeding practices does not significantly differ from one another.

Table 5 (Cluster 2): Independent samples t-test on the newly married women at Nkpologu community and those at Ugbeneajima community on feeding practices

S/No	Item Statements	\bar{X}_G	Communities	N	\bar{X}	SD	F-Cal	P	Decision
1	Consumption of fast foods	4.00	Nkpologu	28	4.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	4.00	0.00			
2	omitting breakfast and having lunch and supper	3.43	Nkpologu	28	3.89	0.31	17.94	0.00	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	3.25	0.64			
3	Take prepared breakfast from farm/work	2.78	Nkpologu	28	3.54	0.51	27.27	0.00	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	2.49	1.12			
4	Eat in- between meals	3.39	Nkpologu	28	4.00	0.00	31.60	0.02	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	3.15	0.54			
5	Skipping lunch	2.74	Nkpologu	28	3.54	0.51	1.06	0.00	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	2.44	0.62			
6	Consume snacks as meals or lunch	3.89	Nkpologu	28	4.00	0.00	28.79	0.0	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	3.85	0.36			
7	Eat adequate meals three times daily	4.00	Nkpologu	28	4.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	4.00	0.00			
8	Take soft drinks daily	4.00	Nkpologu	28	4.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	4.00	0.00			
9	Take dinner at 8pm daily	4.00	Nkpologu	28	4.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	4.00	0.00			

10	Eating from food vendors	2.09	Nkpologu	28	2.96	0.69	12.23	0.00	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	1.75	0.97			
	Mean Cluster	3.43	Nkpologu	28	3.79	0.17	13.40	0.0	S
			Ugbeneajima	73	3.29	0.37		0.0	

Keys: \bar{X}_G =Grand Mean, \bar{X} =Mean of individual groups, N=Group sizes, SD=Standard Deviation, Page | 230
 F-Cal=F-Calculated, P= p-Value, S=Significant, df = 99

The results in Table 5 for cluster 2 indicated that the p-value for each item is less than 0.05 (p-value 0.05). To be statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance, the cluster mean in Table 5 also showed that the p-value was less than 0.05 (p-value 0.05). The mean ratings of the replies from newlywed women living in Nkpologu and those living in Ugbeneajima on feeding habits show a substantial difference. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Findings showed that feeding practices among newly married women were poor as they engaged in unhealthy practices. Inadequate awareness and knowledge of available foods and their nutritional values can be attributed to inappropriate feeding practices, which on long run cause nutrition-related diseases to mother and fetus. This is consistent with the findings of Fulford et al. (2014), who discovered a lack of understanding and compliance with dietary and supplement recommendations in pregnancy. Pregnant women are substantially more mindful of diet than non-pregnant women, according to Szwajcer et al. (2012).

Radio, health workers, friends, family members, television, and posters were the most important sources of nutrition awareness among the women. However, since it was observed from the study that nutritional practices commonly adopted by the newly married women were poor, there is a need to motivate the newly married women to adopt good feeding practices. As such, they are urged to seek preconception treatment at least three months before attempting to conceive so that issues and requirements may be detected early and nutritional status can be improved before getting pregnant. These good practices will not only help to improve their nutritional status and also help to prevent related diseases. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that newly married women should be encouraged to take prepared meals from home this will help them avoid skipping meals. Nutrition seminars and workshop should be organized for newly married women on regular bases to enhance their attitudes and nutritional behavior. Nutrition advocacy can be organized by the primary health care during anti-natal Government should also provide enough land for cultivation.

4. Conclusion

As a result of unhealthy eating practices, newlywed women demonstrated poor nutritional habits. The awareness and interaction of newly married women about nutrition were found to be adequate. The women were primarily aware of nutrition through radio, health workers, friends, family members, television, and posters.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

BIA and COO conceptualized the study and finally edited the manuscript. BIA proposed the methodology while COO finalized the procedure. COO provided some materials and software used during the study. BIA ensured that the data was analyzed and the discussion section was completed. The data curation was done by BIA. All authors approved the final version for publication.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article; further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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